

Scar Endometriosis; A Rare Condition Found In Previous Cesarean Section Scar

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Abstract

A 30 year lady with history of previous three cesarean sections presented with pain in the area of previous healed scar from two years. On clinical examination there was a painful nodule under scar tissue. It was firm in consistency, irregular margins which becomes prominent during menstruation days. On ultrasonography a hypochoic area was found. MRI was non-conclusive and on the basis of clinical examination and history diagnosis of scar endometriosis was made. Whole abnormal tissue was excised by local incision and biopsy sent for histopathology. On biopsy report endometrial glands were detected. This is a biopsy confirmed case of endometriosis on previous scar. Pathogenesis, presentation, diagnosis and modes of treatment have been mentioned below.

Key Words: Endometriosis, scar endometriosis, incisional endometriosis,

INTRODUCTION

An abnormally placed endometrial tissue outside the uterine cavity is called endometriosis. It can be present in fallopian tubes, ovaries, umbilicus, intestines, peritoneum, lungs, nose and in previous scars etc. It can be misdiagnosed or undiagnosed most of the time as it is very rare. Its prevalence is 1.6% only. It is usually found in scars after gynecological operations. Diagnosis is confirmed by histopathological examination and presence of endometrial glands in tissue.

Case Report

A 35 years old female p3,G1 presented with the complaint of lower abdominal pain from 3 years. She had 3 previous cesarean scars. She noticed a tender nodule under the scar tissue which increases in size during menstrual periods. She used many analgesics but pain was not relieved. She was depressed due to this. On examination a tender nodule of 2×1 cm was present under right corner of scar, firm in consistency. On ultrasound examination there was a hypochoic area of 2×1 cm with echogenic shadow. MRI done which was not conclusive. Surgery was planned and local resection of nodule done and sample was sent for histopathological examination. After surgery patient relieved symptoms gradually.

DISCUSSION

In endometriosis endometrial tissue is present in abnormal area outside the uterine cavity. Due to its shape it is also called powder burn lesions. It is usually found in peritoneum. Other sites are less common. It is bluish black in color. On microscopic examination endometrial gland, macrophages containing hemosiderin can be seen in it. A theory says it is formed by retrograde menstrual flow, metaplasia of peritoneum, immune-deficiency and spread by lymphatic or blood.

Scar endometriosis is seen in female patients with previous history of multiple gynecological operations and with incidence of only 0.03-0.15%. It occurs due to implantation of endometrial tissue into abdominal or pelvic fascia, margins of wound or subcutaneous tissue. It may occur in all those incisions where contamination may occur by endometrial tissue like episiotomy, hysterectomy, ectopic pregnancy, tubal-ligation and hysterectomy operations. It may take 4-8 months for development of this condition after operation. It can be neglected or diagnosed as lipoma, granuloma, abscess, hernia, lymphoma or metastatic nodule. Patient with scar endometriosis can be diagnosed by taking proper history of previous operation, pain and increase in size of nodule during menstruation and hypochoic areas on ultrasound and endometrial glands on histopathology examination.

There should be wide local excision of nodule to prevent recurrence. Hormones suppression therapy using danazole or contraceptive pills is not much effective due to more side effects. Any female with suspicion of scar endometriosis should also be evaluated for other conditions as it is a rare condition. Recurrence is much common after wide excision even. So re-evaluation on follow ups is necessary. There is very rare chance of malignant transformation of scar endometriosis. During surgery good soft tissue handling and minimum dissection prevents recurrence.

CONCLUSION

Scar endometriosis has very low incidence and is a rare condition easily misdiagnosed and neglected

or confused with other conditions. History, proper examination, ultrasonography are enough to make diagnosis. Diagnosis can be confirmed on histopathological examination.

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